

Decentralized Optical Line Controller (OLC) for ROADM-free IPoWDM Networks

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Abstract—A novel lightweight Optical Line Controller (OLC) is proposed and validated for IPoWDM networks with no optical bypass. The OLC successfully configures and monitors point-to-point optical links between IPoWDM nodes, without centralized Optical SDN Controllers

Index Terms—Packet-optical, IPoWDM, SDN, OpenConfig

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, hyperscale cloud providers have driven extraordinary advancements in IP over WDM (IPoWDM) technologies, specifically coherent transceivers and packet-switching ASICs. This progress has arrived thanks to the massive increase in traffic growth exchange between data centers. Transceiver line rate is nearly doubling every two years, at a pace much higher than Telco traffic growth. Such evolution is driving Telco Operators to reconsider the way Metro networks are traditionally designed and implemented [1], assessing the so-called opaque or *ROADM-free* networks, which include only IPoWDM nodes without encompassing multi-degree ROADMs [2]. That is, no optical bypass is performed in intermediate nodes and optical connections are operated only on point-to-point links between IPoWDM nodes.

ROADM-free solutions bring potential benefits including the drastic simplification of control procedures. Indeed, there is no need to execute complex routing and spectrum assignment algorithms for transparent mesh topology, complex impairment validation assessment, and complex equalization procedures handling transparent interconnections across multiple ROADMs. Furthermore, failure localization and recovery becomes easier and faster, since no multi-layer procedures are involved. In addition, the overall management procedures are performed in a single-layer by the consolidated IP/MPLS and Segment Routing technology, which can be handled without requiring a team of highly skilled optical experts. Potential drawbacks include additional power consumption due to processing of transit traffic, partially compensated by the reduced number of equipment to be powered on. The additional latency due to electronic conversion and processing in transit nodes appears not relevant, since IPoWDM nodes equipped with

800G transceiver introduce an overall latency lower than 1ms, with negligible jitter. In terms of CAPEX, the ROADM-free solution is generally effective when the amount of transit traffic is limited compared to the transceiver rates. Given the continuous and remarkable increase of transmission rates, ROADM-free solutions are expected to become particularly relevant in multiple metro network scenarios.

In this paper, we design and validate a novel control plane solution specifically designed for ROADM-free point-to-point IPoWDM networks. The simplified yet essential optical network configurations are performed in a decentralized way by lightweight software modules, named Optical Line Controller (OLC), without relying on a centralized Optical SDN Controller.

II. ROADM-FREE NETWORK ARCHITECTURE

Traditionally, IPoWDM nodes have been interconnected using Reconfigurable Optical Add/Drop Multiplexers (ROADMs). A ROADM is built with several elements, mainly ROADMs on Blade (RoB) and Multi-Cast Switches (MCS). Each node degree consists of a RoB, which integrates a pair of Wavelength Selective Switches (WSS) and optical amplifiers, for handling both TX and RX side. For example, Fig. 1(a) shows an IPoWDM node equipped with coherent transceivers that rely on a two-degree ROADM to connect to a different IPoWDM node. The ROADM is composed of two RoB (one for east and one for west sides). A third element, typically a MCS, is also included to serve as add/drop module. This overall multi-layer node architecture enables effective optical bypass in intermediate nodes. Indeed, electronic processing in such ROADM-based optical networks only occurs at the source and destination IPoWDM nodes. On the contrary, a ROADM-free network does not exploit optical bypass, always terminating the optical connection at the adjacent IPoWDM node. Such network infrastructure can be designed according to three different models, depending on the amount of data to be exchanged and the distance between the nodes. In the first ROADM-free network model, the node architecture of Fig. 1(b) is adopted where only one coherent

Fig. 1. (a) Traditional multi-layer architecture with IPoWDM connected via ROADMs; (b) IPoWDM directly connected; (c) IPoWDM connected using multiple transceivers aggregated through RoB.

transceiver per direction is used for the interconnection to the adjacent IPoWDM node. That is, the transceiver is directly attached to the optical fiber. No optical amplification is adopted. This model is suitable for short metro distances (e.g., few tens of km, given the limited sensitivity of the transceivers, in the order of -10dBm) and relatively limited capacity (the one provided by a single transceiver, e.g. 400 or 800Gb/s). In case additional capacity is needed, management problems arise since the line needs to go offline to enable the insertion of coupler/splitters or RoB to serve additional transceivers. In the second model, suitable for larger metro distances (up to few hundreds of km), optical amplification is introduced.

This model, still considering a single transceiver per direction (i.e., relatively limited capacity), may also lead to the same critical upgrade procedures. In the third model, suitable for larger capacity, multiple transceivers per direction are considered. To aggregate multiple signals in a single fiber, different cases are available: (i) *Fixed AWG*. Pros: low cost; low insertion loss; no upgrade issues, scales well to accommodate a large number of transceivers. Cons: rigidity in spectrum allocation due to fixed filtering; it may not be future proof with the increase of baud rate. (ii) *Splitters/Coupler*. Pros: Low cost; no filtering constraints. Cons: possible slight transmission issues due to non-filtered signals; insertion loss increases with the splitting ratio, making it suitable to practically accommodate only very few transceivers. Upgrade issues. (iii) *RoB* (shown in Fig. 1(c)). Pros: relatively low insertion loss; no upgrade issues, no rigidity in spectrum allocation; suitable to accommodate large number of transceivers; future proof with the increase of baud rate. Cons: higher cost.

Each of the above models requires to be properly controlled and managed. Traditional solutions based on centralized Optical SDN controllers appear over-complicated for a set of independent optical links, also considering the complex interactions with the IP Controller (see MANTRA working group and [3], [4]).

III. PROPOSED DECENTRALIZED CONTROL FOR ROADM-FREE NETWORKS

The IP SDN Controller is considered as the single entity controlling the network, directly configuring the IPoWDM nodes. The configuration and monitoring of optical links is instead delegated to lightweight Optical Line Controllers (OLCs). Each OLC has configuration rights to the transceiver

parameters and to the optical elements of the controlled optical link(s). This may include, according to the considered ROADM-free model, WSS and amplifiers in a pair of RoB and in-line amplifiers. In this work, we assume one OLC instance having responsibility of one optical link, in the outgoing direction (i.e., TX side of the link). The OLC has the knowledge of local details (including transceiver capabilities and pluggables/ROB port mapping). It is provided, by the IP Controller or management system, with the IP of the remote node to be connected. Each OLC discovers and configures both local transceiver parameters and pertaining RoB. Furthermore, it is capable to receive monitoring data from all involved elements, including the RX parameters on the connected IPoWDM node. In our implementation, the OLC has been implemented as docker container installed in the IPoWDM node. It is provided with direct access via C-CMIS to the transceiver parameters, and it relies on OpenConfig YANG models via gNMI (or NETCONF) to configure and monitor the intermediate RoBs and amplifiers. Furthermore, the OLC runs a local computation engine performing impairment assessment, spectrum assignment, TX power computation and operational mode assignment for each optical signal activated by the IP Controller. Even if dedicated tools like GNPY or AI models could be adopted as computation engine, in our implementation, given the limited number of supported operational modes and the relatively short distances to cover between IPoWDM nodes (up to few hundreds km), the path computation engine mainly relies on look-up tables over distances, with dynamic feedback based on experienced Pre-FEC and RX power performance.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

The proposed OLC solution has been experimentally validated on a network testbed including two IPoWDM Edgecore nodes, with SONiC Operating System, connected through a three-span optical link, as shown in Fig. 2(a). In the considered scenario, reproducing the most complex implementation of Fig. 1(c), IPoWDM nodes are interconnected through Lumentum RoBs (encompassing WSS and pre/booster per direction) across three spans (240km in total). Two inline amplifiers are used, operating in constant gain mode, to guarantee for each channel a launch power of 0dBm. Each IPoWDM node uses more than one transceiver (two of type 400ZR+ in the experiment). In each IPoWDM node a containerized OLC module has been on-boarded. The OLC has

Fig. 2. (a) Testbed with multiple pluggables and RoBs; (b) Workflow; (c) Wireshark capture.

been equipped with three main plugins: (i) the *gNMI plugin*, enabling both North Bound (towards an IP controller or the Network Administrator) and peer-to-peer (for direct configuration/monitoring functionalities) interfaces; (ii) a *C-CMIS plugin* for the host port/pluggable configuration (the REST-based C-CMIS plugin developed in [4] has been adopted) and (iii) a *gNMI/NETCONF plugin*, being able to perform the configuration of the pertaining RoB (the OpenConfig wavelength-router model has been adopted). In the experiment, gNMI communication to the RoBs is exploited.

Fig. 2(b)-(c) show respectively the proposed workflow and the related Wireshark capture. A connectivity request, including bitrate and remote node, is sent by the IP Controller to OLC of IPoWDM node 1 (OLC1), using the gNMI interface (message 9). Each OLC is aware of the local details including the pluggable capabilities and the port mapping among pluggable modules/RoB. OLC1 selects the frequency to be used for the connectivity (First-Fit policy has been implemented, more advanced solution could be adopted, as in [5]). OLC1 performs the selection and configuration of both pluggables, via C-CMIS plugin (messages 15-20) and the local RoB (RoB1_E), using the gNMI channel (messages 32-35). Then, it triggers, via peer-to-peer gNMI, the OLC at IPoWDM node2 (OLC2), to perform the remote configuration (message 49). OLC2 is responsible to select and configure the local pluggable, via C-CMIS plugin (messages 56-61), and to perform the configuration of the related RoB (i.e., RoB2_W), via gNMI/NETCONF (messages 73-76), acknowledging OLC1 at the end (message 82). The setup of an optical connectivity among the two IPoWDM nodes has been repeated 20 times, collecting the control plane end-to-end setup time. Obtained results show an end-to-end control plane setup time in the order of 0.5s (min

506ms, max 570ms, avg 541ms), while data plane operation is established in around 60s.

V. CONCLUSIONS

A novel Optical Line Controller (OLC) control plane module is proposed and validated on a ROADM-free network, where no optical bypass is performed and multi-degree ROADMs are not deployed. The OLC successfully configures and monitors point-to-point optical links between IPoWDM nodes, without requiring complex centralized Optical SDN Controllers and related MANTRA Architectures.

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